

An LLM-Based Approach to Generating Authorization Policies for Data Products

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Abstract. A data product is the architectural cornerstone enabling data sharing and it is usually designed as a service that exposes an interface where the methods for accessing the offered data are defined. Along with the interface, it is essential to define authorization rules that determine who can access a given data product and under what conditions. In this context Policy-as-Code is helpful to define these rules that allow the operator to properly configure the platform responsible for enabling the data sharing under the requests expressed by the data owner.

In this paper, we investigate whether large language models (LLMs) can be leveraged to reduce the effort required of data platform operators by automatically generating rules from data owners' natural language policies. We propose a pipeline that combines LLMs with retrieval-augmented generation (RAG), and we evaluate it through a practical implementation based on the rules expressed using Rego: a policy language supported by OPA (Open Policy Agent).

Keywords: Policy as Code · Rego · Data Mesh.

1 Introduction

According to the Data Mesh [4], data management can be improved if data are seen as products. Like any other types of product, it must be defined who has the responsibility of the data product, which are the resources available for managing the associated data, and how the data can be accessed. About the last point, service-based approach are adopted, and data products [10] expose interfaces (e.g., REST-based) that define the methods for accessing the data. While these interfaces enable the data accessibility, such accessibility must be properly regulated to ensure the *data sovereignty* that recognizes the data owner as the holder of full rights and responsibility over the product's lifecycle. Policies are employed to regulate data use. Policies encompass a broad set of rules that govern the data lifecycle, and they may be influenced by external regulations.

A critical aspect in the policy definition is related to the tension between two actors: (i) the data owner, who defines the policies based on complete knowledge of the data; and (ii) platform operators, i.e., those with the technical skills to formally define the rules, but who lack a full understanding of the domain context. An important example of this dichotomy is authorization policies. The data

owner specifies who can interact with the data product and what actions they can perform. As the policies expressed by the data owner are usually not directly actionable, an additional step is required to configure the system to enforce the policies when the data product is accessed. However, converting policies from the data owner’s expression to the system’s code remains a manual process, which prevents the full automation that the policy-as-code paradigm aims to achieve.

This research addresses the gap between the formulation of policies and their implementation as code. The aim is to automate the generation of authorization policies by enabling data owners, who may lack technical expertise, to define policies in natural language. These policies are then automatically translated into the system’s technical code, even when its variables remain unknown to the data owners, within a system potentially distributed across multiple consumers. This capability aligns with the principles of data mesh: it reinforces domain ownership by giving data owners complete control over authorization policies without technical mediation, and it promotes self-service by reducing reliance on platform specialists while enabling direct governance. As a result, the need to involve platform operators for every new policy is eliminated, reducing their workload beyond the initial setup and actively supporting the automation of service governance.

Specifically, the research explores using Large Language Models (LLMs) to generate policy as code. The focus is on Rego [8] authorization policies for regulating access to data products, in a scenario where the Data Mesh is implemented through REST services [5] and OPA is used as the access-management solution that applies the policies. LLMs potential to generate policy code to manage authorization to data products remains largely unexplored, also considering that, while the data platform operator has technical knowledge of the system in which policies are executed, LLMs lack this awareness. This paper addresses this issue by using historical examples and system-specific information to improve LLMs’ generative capabilities, enabling them to produce rules consistent with the application scenario and aligned with the underlying technical structure. To this end, we propose an extensible pipeline for generation using Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) and a Knowledge Base (KB), which provide the necessary background information for the LLM. Finally, we evaluated the pipeline’s effectiveness through a practical implementation.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work. Section 3 presents the policy generation pipeline, while Section 4 describes the practical implementation conducted. Finally, Section 5 concludes by summarizing the results and possible future work.

2 Related Work

A specific area of research on code generation with LLMs [3,11] has focused on policies, particularly within the policy-as-code paradigm. This line of work has gained traction in various fields, notably for example in robotics [6,1]. However, the focus of our work is on access policies expressed as code. Some stud-

ies have proposed pipelines for generating access policies using LLMs, offering a starting point for exploring LLM-based approaches in this domain. For instance, [9] explores the ability of LLMs to generate eXtensible Access Control Markup Language (XACML) policies from natural language input, while [7] presents a pipeline that incorporates RAG-like knowledge integration to generate Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) policies. In the specific case of Rego as the chosen policy language, only a very limited number of studies have explored the use of LLMs for policy generation. A notable contribution is provided by [2], which examines the use of LLMs to generate Rego-based access control policies. The primary focus of that work is on private LLM deployments, driven by privacy and security concerns, as organizational policies often encode sensitive business logic. The study also observes that, when relying on public LLMs such as GPT, the generation of correct and complete policies typically requires extensive prompt engineering across multiple iterations.

3 Policy as Code Generation Pipeline

The objective of our work is to design an end-to-end pipeline specifically tailored to the context of data products. Unlike previous approaches, our focus is on assisting data owners who lack the expertise to craft structured prompts. The pipeline reduces the technical burden by minimizing the need for manual policy implementation by technical staff and, most importantly, enables automated policy generation.

Specifically, as shown in Figure 1, the generation workflow begins with a target policy written in natural language as **input**. Since data owners may lack technical expertise, they only need to provide the new policy in natural language. The pipeline consists of the following steps: 1) *Knowledge Base Initialization*, 2) *Policy Retrieval via RAG*, 3) *Prompt Design and Policy Generation via LLM*, and 4) *Policy Validation*.

The pipeline’s structure is motivated to ensure that generated policies are directly applicable within the system governing access to data products. To maintain consistency, policies must follow specific technical conventions, such as using predefined attributes and values in Rego. To provide the LLM with the necessary context, a Knowledge Base initialization phase was introduced to store both the operational environment and existing policies. Rather than feeding all existing policies to the LLM, they are stored in a vector database and retrieved on demand for efficiency, motivating the use of RAG. This information is provided to the LLM, which generates the new policy. Since these policies govern authorization, correctness is essential for system security; therefore, the generated output is validated.

Finally, the **output** is the policy translated into Rego.

Rego policies typically consist of three core components: the resource to which the rule applies, the subjects governed by the policy, and the actions they are permitted to perform, along with any additional conditions. Each policy in Rego is defined as an **allow** rule within a Rego document. All conditions within a single

Fig. 1: Pipeline for Policy as Code Generation

rule must be true for it to be evaluated to be true (logical AND). Across multiple allow rules, a logical OR applies: if at least one rule returns true, the request is allowed; otherwise, access is denied by default. Rego is well-suited for fine-grained authorization in data products, as it supports the declarative definition of attributes and system-specific conditions required to access a resource.

3.1 Knowledge Base Initialization

The KB is an integrated repository of information for the LLMs. To consistently carry out the generation task and ensure compliance, the LLM can take advantage of a KB that is composed of two sections. Without a well-structured KB, the LLM would lack the semantic foundation and technical precedents necessary to generate rules that align with existing policies and satisfy the system’s compliance requirements.

- **Historical Policies:** authorization policies that have been formally approved and enforced within the system. Each historical policy is stored in two forms: (i) a version written by the data owner in natural language, and (ii) a corresponding Rego code. This dual representation allows the LLM to learn from concrete examples by mapping natural language requirements to proven code implementations, illustrating how attributes, values, and functions are used in practice.
- **Contextual Information:** includes all the technical information needed to formulate the code. For Rego, this context may cover the permitted actions, the roles and relevant attributes.

Maintaining and updating this dual section repository enables the model to continuously evolve its policy generation capabilities while ensuring compliance.

3.2 Policy Retrieval via RAG

Policy retrieval, which implements the RAG paradigm, consists of extracting from the KB the historical policies that are most similar to the new one to be generated. These policies, referred to as *Retrieved Policies*, are then provided to the LLM, serving as examples.

Fig. 2: Retrieval-Augmented Generation for retrieving policies

Loading the entire policy archive into the model would be both resource-intensive and unnecessary. Instead, the natural language versions of the historical policies are embedded using a Sentence Transformer and indexed in a Vector Database, such as Pinecone, enabling lexical similarity search. When a new policy is generated, as shown in Figure 2, its natural language formulation is encoded into an embedding vector. This vector is then compared with those stored in the database using cosine similarity. Both embedding and retrieval are performed exclusively on the natural language representations, and the top-ranked results are extracted and used in the LLM’s prompt. Employing RAG instead of a simple prompt containing all policies makes the model extensible, allowing new policies to be easily retrieved and incorporated.

3.3 Prompt Design and Policy Generation via LLM

At the core of the pipeline lies the generation process, with particular emphasis on prompt formulation. Through the prompt, the LLM is guided during generation and provided with all the necessary information. For this reason, the prompt is structured into distinct modules, each serving a specific purpose:

- **Target Policy:** the policy as expressed by the data owner in natural language. The description should contain three key elements when present: the *Data Product* to which the rule applies, the *Subject* expected to comply, and the *Action* permitted or prohibited, potentially qualified by other conditions. From this untagged text, the LLM extracts these elements and prepares them for translation into code.
- **Knowledge Base Elements:** The *Retrieved Policies* in both their natural-language and code, and the *Contextual Information*.
- **Rules:** *Generation Rules* consists of general syntactic and semantic guidelines that apply to policy generation, as conventions for Rego syntax and strategies to minimise hallucinations, for example, by prohibiting the invention of new values to assign. *System Rules*, includes constraints and requirements specific to the target system. These rules define, for example, the

correct use of functions and arguments, or specify which roles hold special permissions, referencing precise elements stored in the KB.

- **Structured Reasoning:** Inspired by the chain-of-thought paradigm, this module guides the LLM through a step-by-step process to improve generative accuracy: first by identifying the Data Product, Subject, and Action (DP-S-A) of the new policy; then by comparing these elements with those extracted from historical policies; and finally by generating the code while adapting the collected information.

Modules such as Rules, Structured Reasoning, and Contextual Information are set up by the operator during an initial configuration. In contrast, the Retrieved Policies module changes dynamically depending on the Target Policy. The prompt is designed so that the data owner only needs to provide the policy in natural language, minimizing their technical involvement.

3.4 Policy Validation

Before deployment, each generated policy must be validated to ensure it is correct and executable within the target environment. In the context of Rego, one possible approach to validating generated policies before deployment involves simulating the target environment with a dedicated OPA implementation and verifying that the policies comply with the original natural language requirements. Since this is a complex aspect to implement, the final validation phase is not addressed in the current work. As discussed in the next Section, thanks to the availability of the original target policy with the correct Rego implementation as the gold standard, it is possible to avoid performing the simulation and instead directly compare each generated policy against the gold standard. Nevertheless, validation remains an important step for accurately assessing policies and, for this reason, is left as a direction for future research.

4 Implementation

This section provides information about the implementation of the proposed approach. The related code is publicly available at the repository <https://github.com/ISGroup-Polimi/RegoGenerator>.

4.1 Dataset Selection and Implementation Setup

To test the proposed pipeline, a public GitHub repository¹ containing over 100 policies was used. These policies determine the authorization to access and perform actions on specific resources by particular user types. They follow the standard pattern of specifying a subject, an object, and an action. The policies also make use of system-specific functions, which increases the overall complexity and provides a realistic set of examples.

¹ <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/fleetdm/fleet/refs/heads/main/server/authz/policy.rego>

```

knowledge_base = {
  "actions": [],
  "user_specified_functions": [
    {
      "description": "",
      "definition": ""
    }
  ],
  "roles": [],
  "policies": [
    {
      "nlp": "",
      "rego": ""
    },
    {
      "nlp": "",
      "rego": ""
    }
  ],
  "user_specified_actions": [],
  "specified_actions": [
    {
      "description": "",
      "definition": ""
    }
  ]
}

```

Fig. 3: KB as a JSON file

```

template = """
You are an assistant generating Rego policies.
Inputs:
- New policy (NL): {query}
- Retrieved policies: {retrieved_policies}
- System elements: Actions {actions}, Roles {roles}, functions {functions}

Rules:
- RULES FOR YOUR GENERATION: do not invent any values...
- RULES SPECIFIC TO THE SYSTEM: follow system constraints...

Task:
1. Identify SUBJECT, OBJECT, ACTION from the new policy.
2. Identify SUBJECT, OBJECT, ACTION in the retrieved policies.
3. Match OBJECT with retrieved policies and copy object.type from the best match
4. Generate an allow block in Rego:
  - Preserve object.type.
  - Generate SUBJECT and ACTION using retrieved policies and knowledge base.
  - Follow the high-level rules specified above.
5. Output the Rego code;
"""

```

Fig. 4: Prompt template

Knowledge Base: Eighty percent of the policies specified in the file were designated as historical policies. For each of these, the natural-language description and the corresponding Rego implementation were extracted and saved in the KB. The remaining twenty percent were reserved as test policies. The policies in the dataset clearly exhibited the three main elements of interest: the object, represented as the attribute `object.type` in Rego, was interpreted as the identifier of the Data Product; the subject, commonly defined using the attribute `subject.global_role` in rego or through the `team.role` function, was interpreted as a potential Data Consumer; and the action, typically specified as the attribute `action`, indicated the operation performed by the role on the object. In addition, specific functions were used to express additional conditions. For the context, the same Rego file was used as it included the elements necessary to write the rules, such as the definitions of permitted actions, user-specific actions, recognized roles, and other system-specific constructs. Both the historical policies and the contextual information were stored in the KB, represented as a JSON file, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Vector Database Setup: In the practical implementation, historical policies were embedded and indexed in a Pinecone representations. A separate index was created for each configuration of historical policies and test set under evaluation. Each index was programmatically instantiated via the Pinecone API with dimensionality set to match the embedding size of the `all-mpnet-base-v2` model (768). Cosine similarity was specified as the distance metric, and the index was deployed in a serverless configuration on AWS (`us-east-1`). This ensured both compatibility with the embedding model and scalability of the retrieval layer. The decision to use only natural language representations was motivated by two main factors. First, since the target policy is also provided in natural language, similarity can be more effectively measured at the textual level. Second, Rego policies tend to follow a highly uniform structure—with recur-

ring elements such as `allow` blocks and standard `object`, `subject`, and `action` attributes—making code-based embeddings less informative and less effective for retrieval. For embedding generation, we employed the SentenceTransformer `all-mpnet-base-v2` model. This model was chosen because it provides state-of-the-art performance for semantic similarity tasks in English while offering a good balance between computational efficiency and embedding dimensionality (768). During retrieval, cosine similarity was used to measure semantic closeness, as it is the standard metric for dense vector spaces. We set the retrieval depth to $k = X$ (empirically tuned based on validation performance as discussed in the results paragraph), which allowed us to include sufficient retrieved policies without overwhelming the LLM prompt. These retrieved policies were then injected into the LLM prompt to guide policy generation.

4.2 Policies Generation

GPT-4o was selected for policy generation due to its knowledge of Rego. Figure 4 provides a short sample version of the prompt used. The necessary elements were incorporated into the prompt:

- The target policy set was derived from 20% of the dataset and served as input for generation. The remaining 80% of the policies were used to construct the KB, and multiple random configurations were tested—always maintaining an 80-20 split between historical and target policies.
- K-retrieved policies were selected by comparison with the target policy.
- Contextual information defines details such as the actions, the roles, and environment-specific elements such as user-defined functions.
- Generation rules directed the model to rely exclusively on provided values and not to invent new ones. In particular, the model was required to identify the `object.type` Rego value, representing the data product, using only values found in the retrieved policies. Additional instructions were included to prevent common LLM errors, such as omitting critical elements.
- System rules addressed the use of specific functions by providing additional explanations not available in the KB alone, as well as guidance on the use of certain roles in specific scenarios.
- Structured reasoning was employed to guide the LLM through a step-by-step process: identifying and explicitly stating in natural language the `subject`, `object`, and `action` of the new policy; repeating this process for each retrieved policy; documenting the reasoning behind each mapping; and ensuring that the elements, especially the `object.type`, were correctly aligned before proceeding with the code generation.

After this initial setup, the model can translate natural language instructions into Rego code. The process is fully automated: the data owner only needs to provide the target policy, while all other information is retrieved and updated automatically. We tested the prompt on all target policies in the testing set, keeping the main prompt unchanged while dynamic information, such as retrieved policies, is customized automatically within the pipeline.

4.3 Pipeline Validation

Since we do not have access to the system in which the policies are actually enforced, the valuation approach relies on comparing the generated policies with the gold standard policies, which are available in the repository and can be attributed to the platform operator. Our comparison method is based on checking whether the generated policy uses the exact same semantic as the gold standard. This approach can produce false negatives, as the same policy could potentially be expressed in alternative ways. However, because Rego is a relatively rigid language, operating with a strict set of attributes and values, and accuracy is our priority. We treated policies with different attributes or functions as non-matching, while those using identical syntax were considered matching. Minor formatting differences, such as the order of values or extra spaces, which do not affect OPA’s behavior, were ignored. This part of the evaluation is referred to as **Semantic Comparison (SC)** and was conducted by a human expert with the assistance of GPT to expedite the process. Since GPT may produce errors in the assessment, its role was limited to presenting pairs of policies and indicating whether they matched or not, while the human supervisor reviewed and approved or rejected GPT’s decisions.

A second method involved an **Average Textual Similarity (ATS)** evaluation performed using `SequenceMatcher` to measure the structural and lexical closeness between the generated policy and its gold standard counterpart. A high similarity score in this comparison indicates stylistic coherence and a reduction in so-called “hallucinations,” i.e., the introduction of attributes or functions not present in the reference examples.

4.4 Results

Multiple random configurations were tested. To create these configurations, including *A*, *B*, *C*, *D*, *E-DP*, and the variants *A-DP* and *B-DP*, the dataset of policies was split randomly, always maintaining an 80-20 ratio between historical and target policies to explore a variety of scenarios. Each configuration generates a set of historical policies, which are embedded and stored in a Pinecone vector database with a separate index for each configuration, while the corresponding target policy sets are saved as pickle files.

In real-world scenarios, the available policies may be limited. For this reason, we tested the model with different values of k , i.e., the number of retrieved policies provided to the LLM. Table 1 reports the results for two different test-KB configurations, A and B. Studying the effect of varying k , we observe that even with $k = 1$, providing the LLM with very limited knowledge, the model achieves an accuracy between 45% and 58%. As k increases, and thus more information is provided, the model’s performance improves significantly. With the same level of $k = 10$, we achieved excellent results, as shown in Table 2, with accuracy reaching up to 87%. The exception is configuration B, which shows a lower result. This can be attributed to the fact that configuration B included

Table 1: Validation Results with different number of retrieved policies

<i>Config.</i>	<i>k</i>	SC	ATS
A	1	58.3%	0.77
	5	79.2%	0.87
	10	87.5%	0.88
B	1	45.8%	0.80
	5	66.7%	0.84
	10	66.7%	0.88

Table 2: Validation Results with different configurations but same k

<i>Config.</i>	<i>k</i>	SC	ATS
A	10	87.5%	0.88
B	10	66.7%	0.88
C	10	87.0%	0.88
D	10	87.0%	0.90

Table 3: Validation Results if at least one policy for each DP is in the KB

<i>Config.</i>	<i>k</i>	SC	ATS
E-DP	10	95.7%	0.91
A-DP	10	95.8%	0.90
B-DP	10	87.5%	0.89

policies for which there were no other policies in the knowledge base on the same data product, so the LLM could not infer the correct attribute to use in Rego.

Conversely, we tested the pipeline in optimal scenarios where each policy had a data product with at least one corresponding policy in the knowledge base, expecting that this feature would yield improved results compared to the original configurations such as A or B. The results, shown in Table 3, refer to the A-DP, B-DP, and E-DP configurations, which meet this requirement by modifying the set of target policies. As shown, configuration A increases from an SC of 87.5% to 95.8% when the data product is present in the KB (A-DP), while B rises from 66.7% to 87.5% (B-DP). Achieving higher accuracy requires ensuring that at least one policy per data product is present in the KB, which is not a particularly restrictive limitation. Alternatively, a predefined dataset of all valid attribute values could be integrated, although this would require additional memory resources. While the requirement for an initial setup could be seen as a limitation, some manual configuration of initial attribute values is generally unavoidable, and in practice, a data product is rarely governed by a single policy—especially in distributed systems where multiple policies coexist and several actors exchange data.

In terms of average textual similarity, the results were satisfactory, consistently exceeding 88% for $k = 10$. The differences can be attributed to minor, non-semantic variations, such as formatting, which do not affect the logical behavior of the policy, as illustrated in Figure 5a. Moreover, to maintain a selective validation process, certain null-check conditions present in the gold policy but omitted in the generated one were treated as errors, as for Figure 5b. To conclude, the dataset used was originally intended for manual use rather than automatic generation. This setup allowed us to evaluate the model in more realistic scenarios, where actors may provide imprecise instructions and the LLM relies on

a knowledge base that is not always fully comprehensive. As a result, we were also able to assess the handling of ambiguous or polysemous instructions. The LLM interprets natural language queries by comparing them to previously encoded policies. Even when a term differs from the one used in Rego, the model can correctly identify the corresponding data product as long as the term has been associated with the same meaning in past policies. This mechanism ensures consistent and accurate policy generation despite variations in wording.

<pre>Generated Rego Policy: allow { object.type == "team" object.id != 0 subject.global_role == [admin, maintainer, observer_plus, observer] action == read } Expected (Gold Standard) Rego policy: allow { object.type == "team" object.id != 0 subject.global_role == [admin, maintainer, observer, observer_plus] action == read }</pre>	<pre>Generated Rego Policy: allow { not_is_null(object.team_id) object.type == "mdm_apple_setup_assistant" team_role(subject, object.team_id) == [admin, maintainer] action == {read, write} } Expected (Gold Standard) Rego policy: allow { not_is_null(object.team_id) object.team_id != 0 object.type == "mdm_apple_setup_assistant" team_role(subject, object.team_id) == [admin, maintainer] action == {read, write} }</pre>
(a) Semantically equivalent policies	(b) Semantically different policies

Fig. 5: Generated Rego policies vs. gold standard examples.

5 Discussion and Future Work

This work investigated the use of LLMs to support the generation of Rego policies, a task typically handled by platform operators. Policies defined by data owners establish authorization rules for their data products. The objective is to alleviate the operational workload on platform teams while empowering data owners with greater direct control over their assets and promoting automation in policy creation. To support this objective, a pipeline is proposed that integrates a KB, utilized to furnish the LLM with the necessary context to translate natural language into Rego, with a RAG module that retrieves previously implemented policies. The pipeline was evaluated in a practical setting, demonstrating that, once properly configured and validated, new policies can be generated and verified at least through direct comparison against gold standard implementations. These results illustrate the potential of LLMs to automate policy-as-code generation for data product authorization control, leveraging structured reasoning and predefined rule definitions. Such an approach points toward a future in which data owners can autonomously define and enforce access policies, thereby reducing the need for continuous intervention of platform operators and enabling higher degrees of automation in authorization governance after the initial setup.

Despite these promising outcomes, several limitations remain, which outline clear directions for future work. First, the current implementation lacks a comprehensive automated validation stage. Integrating validation mechanisms through OPA would enable end-to-end policy verification. Second, to the best of our knowledge, the proposed pipeline represents the first approach explicitly designed to generate Rego policies directly from data owners' natural language inputs. While this novelty is an important contribution, it also constrains the

scope of the evaluation. Future research could extend this foundation to address more complex policy scenarios, such as supporting multiple policy types, federated environments with richer and more distributed contextual information, and heterogeneous historical policy landscapes. Potential improvements could also include employing more advanced retrieval techniques (e.g., graph-based RAG) and incorporating more testing with multiple LLM models and simulation strategies to strengthen policy reliability. Overall, the proposed pipeline establishes a baseline for further research on the automated generation and validation of authorization policies, opening promising avenues for advancing authorization governance through LLM-based approaches.

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